

Data Management Plan Template

The aim of this template¹ and guidance (text in italics/grey) is to assist in preparing Data Management Plans (DMP) for FLUP's Master Dissertations and Doctoral Theses, as well as for Grant Applications and Research Projects.

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PROJECT – GENERAL INFORMATION	
TYPE:	<i>Indicate Master Dissertation, PhD Thesis, EU/FCT or any other funding/grant organisation/programme</i>
ID:	<i>Indicate the ID of the project</i>
ACRONYM:	<i>Indicate the acronym of the project</i>
NAME:	<i>Indicate the full name of the project</i>
PI:	<i>Indicate the <u>name</u>, <u>ORCID</u>, and <u>email</u> of the Master/PhD student or the principal investigator of the project</i>
INSTITUTION(S):	<i>Indicate the <u>name</u> and <u>ROR</u> (VIAF, or other ID) of the institution(s) of the Master/PhD student or partner/collaboration institutions of the project</i>
PERIOD:	<i>Indicate the full period of the project (DD-MM-YYYY / DD-MM-YYYY)</i>
WEBSITE:	<i>Indicate the URI of the project's website if there is any</i>

PROJECT - ABSTRACT	
<i>Insert the abstract of the project here.</i>	
KEYWORDS:	<i>Indicate 3 to 5 keywords.</i>

¹ This document is primarily based on the Horizon Europe guidelines and adapted from the FCT Data Management Plan template.

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN – HISTORY OF CHANGES

VERSION	PUBLICATION DATE	CONTRIBUTOR(S)	CHANGE(S)
2.0	20.10.2025	Francisco Lopes	– Added section “Third countries associated with the UNESCO Research and Training Programme”.
1.1	10.06.2025	Alice Guedes, João Faria	– Reformatted to align with other deliverables templates. – Updated section ‘1. Data Information’: . Added reference to the applicable General Annexes and introduced hyperlink leading to General Annexes 2025-2026.
1.0	05.05.2025	Teresa Sá	– Initial version.

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN – ANNEXES

DOCUMENT	SHORT DESCRIPTION/URI
DEspacho GR 12_10_2024_Politica de Ciência Aberta-merged.pdf	U.Porto policy on Open Science. https://sigarra.up.pt/up/pt/LEGISLACAO_GERAL.ver_legislacao?p_nr=48092

1. DATA INFORMATION

1.1	<p>Will you reuse existing data for this project?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
1.1.1	<p>If Yes, which existing data will be reused and under which terms of use?</p> <p>– Indicate which existing data you will reuse and state constraints on the reuse of third-party data if there are any.</p>
1.1.2	<p>If Yes, which data type(s) and format(s) will be reused?</p> <p>– Indicate the type of data. E.g., numeric (databases, spreadsheets), textual (documents), image, audio, video, GIS, mixed media.</p> <p>– Indicate the data format. I.e., the way in which the data is encoded for storage is often reflected by the filename extension (e.g., xls, csv, docx, txt, pdf, tiff, jpeg, wav, rdf).</p> <p>– Justify the use of certain formats. E.g., decisions may be based on staff expertise within the host organisation, a preference for open formats, standards accepted by data repositories, widespread usage within the research community, or on the software or equipment that will be used.</p> <p>❖ Recommendation: give preference to open and standard formats as they facilitate sharing and long-term preservation and reuse of data. Several repositories provide lists of such ‘preferred formats’.</p>
1.2	<p>Will new data be created and/or produced in this project?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p>– <u>If Yes</u>, please indicate what data will be created and/or produced.</p>

1.2.1	<p>If Yes, which data will be created and/or produced and under which terms of use?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Indicate which data will be created and/or produced, and state constraints on creating and/or producing data if there are any.
1.2.2	<p>If Yes, which data type(s) and format(s) will be created and/or produced?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Indicate the type of data. E.g., numeric (databases, spreadsheets), textual (documents), image, audio, video, GIS, mixed media. – Indicate the data format. I.e., the way in which the data is encoded for storage is often reflected by the filename extension (e.g., xlsx, csv, docx, txt, pdf, tiff, jpeg, wav, rdf). – Justify the use of certain formats. E.g., decisions may be based on staff expertise within the host organisation, a preference for open formats, standards accepted by data repositories, widespread usage within the research community, or on the software or equipment that will be used. ❖ Recommendation: give preference to open and standard formats as they facilitate sharing and long-term preservation and reuse of data. Several repositories provide lists of such 'preferred formats'.
1.3	<p>How much data storage will this project require in total?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 0 – 10 GB <input type="checkbox"/> 100 – 1000 GB <input type="checkbox"/> 10 – 100 GB <input type="checkbox"/> >1000 GB</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – If relevant, please justify the volume estimate.
1.4	<p>To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside this project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Indicate the 'utility' of your data to other, e.g., projects, topics, disciplines, fields, communities.

2. DOCUMENTATION AND METADATA

2.1	<p>What documentation will accompany the data?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Describe what other documentation is needed to enable reuse. Include information needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data reuse E.g., information will be recorded in a database with links to each item, a 'readme' text file, codebooks, lab notebooks, file headers; definition of variables, units of measurement; data cleaning, analyses). – Indicate how the data will be organised during the project. E.g., mention conventions, version control, folder structures, folders and files naming. Consistent, well-ordered research data will be easier to find, understand, and reuse.
2.2	<p>Will there be metadata associated with the data?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes Language: _____ <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – If Yes, please indicate which metadata will be provided and in which language (according to ISO 639-3 code: e.g., por, spa, eng, fre) to help others identify and discover the data. To be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), data must be accompanied with descriptive information in the form of metadata.
2.2.1	<p>If Yes, will the metadata follow any standard(s)?</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Where these are in place, researchers are advised to use community metadata standards. The Research Data Alliance maintains a Directory of Metadata Standards (http://rd-alliance.github.io/metadata-directory/). - Indicate if the metadata will be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed. ❖ <i>Tip: depositing data in a certified or trustworthy repository (e.g., CoreTrustSeal, Nestor Seal, ISO 16363 certification) will typically involve providing information about the data according to a metadata standard scheme (e.g., Dublin Core, DataCite Metadata Schema). If this is the case for the data described in this plan, that can be specified here.</i> ❖ Recommendation: contact FLUP/U.Porto's Research Data Management (RDM) support staff for further advice on metadata.
2.2.2	<p>Will the data use controlled vocabularies?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>If Yes, please indicate the controlled vocabularies that apply and if they are available as Linked Open Data (LOD).</i>

3. STORAGE AND SECURITY OF DATA AND METADATA	
3.1	<p>Is there a policy in place for data storage and backups during the project?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Unknown</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>If Yes, please indicate the policy document and link (when available). Policies and other relevant documents may be included as attachments to the DMP if this is considered necessary - reference should be made to this in the 'D. Data Management Plan – Annexes' table.</i>
3.2	<p>Where will data and metadata be stored and backed up during the research?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Specify where the data and metadata will be stored and backed up during the project. E.g., Institution's networked research storage and/or other.</i> - <i>Describe the type of backup: cloud backup, differential backup, FTP backup, full backup, full computer backup, incremental backup, local backup, mirror backup, offsite backup, remote backup.</i> - <i>Describe the frequency of backup.</i> ❖ Recommendation: give preference to the use of robust, managed storage with automatic backup and data security, such as provided by IT support services of FLUP/U.Porto. Storing project data only on laptops, standalone hard drives, or external storage devices such as USB sticks is not recommended.
3.3	<p>How will data security and protection of sensitive data be taken care of during the research?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Not applicable (no sensitive data).</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Default security measures of the institution's networked research storage.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Additional security measures.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Consider data protection, particularly if your data is sensitive (e.g., containing personal data, politically sensitive information; information relating to religion and health, trade secrets, national security information). Describe the main risks and how these will be managed.</i> - <i>Describe how the data will be recovered in the event of an incident.</i> - <i>Indicate who will have access to the data during the research and how access to data is controlled, especially in collaborative partnerships.</i>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Indicate which institutional data protection policies are in place (e.g., funder, U.Porto, FLUP). Policies and other relevant documents may be included as attachments to the DMP if this is considered necessary - reference should be made to this in the 'D. Data Management Plan – Annexes' table. – If '<u>Additional security measures</u>' has been selected, please specify which ones.
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4. PERSONAL DATA, INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS, AND OWNERSHIP

4.1	<p>Will you process and/or store personal data during the project?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
4.1.1	<p>If Yes, how will compliance with legislation and (institutional) regulation on personal data be ensured?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Ensure that when dealing with personal data protection laws (e.g., GDPR) are complied: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> . Gain informed consent for preservation and/or sharing of personal data. . Consider anonymisation, pseudonymisation or encryption of personal data for preservation and/or sharing (truly anonymous data are no longer considered personal data. The main difference with anonymisation is that pseudonymisation is reversible. Encryption is a special case of pseudonymisation; the encryption key is stored separately from the data, namely by a trusted third-party). – Indicate whether there is a managed access procedure in place for authorised users of personal data. ❖ Recommendation, GDPR: check the Portuguese transposition of EC legislation (https://diariodarepublica.pt/dr/detalhe/lei/58-2019-123815982, e.g., article 31.º). <i>Seek advice on Personal data, intellectual property, copyright and rights management issues that apply to the resources from specialised support staff at FLUP/U.Porto.</i>
4.2	<p>How will ownership of the data and intellectual property rights to the data be managed?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Specify who will be the owner of the data. I.e., who will have the rights, but also who will be responsible to control access (e.g., data access committee, for requests to personal/sensitive or other data). Note that an institution may be the owner and have the rights, but there should be someone responsible – please provide contact). Ensure that these matters of rights to control access to data for multi-partner projects and multiple data owners are covered in the consortium agreement. – Indicate whether intellectual property rights (e.g., Database Directive, sui generis rights) are affected. If so, describe which and how they will be dealt with. ❖ Recommendation: check institutional/funder requirements.

5. DATA SHARING AND LONG-TERM PRESERVATION

5.1	<p>How will data be selected for long-term preservation?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> All data resulting from the project will be preserved for at least __ years. <input type="checkbox"/> Other.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – If <u>Other</u>, please specify: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> . What data must be retained or destroyed for contractual, legal, ethical, or regulatory purposes. . How it will be decided what data to keep. . The data to be long-term preserved.
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5.2	<p>What data will be made available for reuse?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> All data resulting from the project will be made available. <input type="checkbox"/> Other.</p> <p>– <i>If Other, please specify:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> . What data will be made available for reuse. This selection may differ from the data that is preserved, when the data are so large that it is unfeasible to deposit the data in a repository in its entirety, or if there are reasons that prohibit making data available for reuse. . If there are any restrictions on the reuse of the data, or if it is necessary to restrict access to certain parts of the data or to apply a data sharing agreement, describe how and why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. . What actions will be taken to overcome or to minimise restrictions. <p>❖ <i>Recommendation: as much as possible, research data should be made publicly available for reuse. Funders are increasingly requiring, as a minimum, that the data underpinning research papers should be made available to other researchers at the time of the article’s publication, unless there are valid reasons not to do so. The guiding principle here is ‘as open as possible, as closed as necessary.’ Due consideration is given to aspects such as privacy, public security, ethical limitations, property rights and commercial interests. Policies and other relevant documents may be included as attachments to the DMP if this is considered necessary - reference should be made to this in the ‘D. Data Management Plan – Annexes’ table.</i></p>
5.3	<p>When will the data be available for reuse, and for how long will the data be available?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Data available as soon as archived in a repository.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Data available as soon as the article is published.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Data available upon completion of the project.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Data available after completion of project (with embargo).</p> <p>– <i>Indicate when (include expected timely release) and for how long the data will be made available.</i></p> <p>– <i>Indicate the reason and duration of any embargo periods.</i></p> <p>– <i>Indicate whether exclusive use of the data will be claimed and, if so, why and for how long.</i></p> <p>– <i>Indicate whether data sharing will be postponed or restricted (e.g., to publish, protect intellectual property, or seek patents).</i></p> <p>❖ <i>Recommendation: as much as possible, research data should be made publicly available for reuse. Funders are increasingly requiring, as a minimum, that the data underpinning research papers should be made available to other researchers at the time of the article’s publication, unless there are valid reasons not to do so.</i></p>
5.4	<p>In which repository/archive will the data be deposited and made available for reuse?</p> <p>– <i>Indicate where the data will be deposited and made available for reuse, beyond the end of the project/grant.</i></p> <p>❖ <i>Tip 1: all beneficiaries of FCT funding may deposit their research data in the Polen Research Data Repository (https://repositorio.polen.fccn.pt/), which is managed by FCCN, the FCT National Scientific Computing Unit.</i></p> <p>❖ <i>Tip 2: check r3Data (https://www.re3data.org/), FAIRsharing (https://fairsharing.org/), Repository Finder (https://repositoryfinder.datacite.org/), or OpenDOAR (https://v2.sherpa.ac.uk/opensoar/), to help you find an appropriate repository to deposit your research data. Typically, appropriate data repositories adhere to the following minimum selection criteria: provision of persistent and unique identifiers; use of metadata standards that are broadly accepted by the scientific community; provision of information that is publicly available; enabling access to data under well-specified conditions and following open and standard access protocols; provision of information about licenses and permissions; ensuring persistence of data and metadata.</i></p>

5.5	<p>Does the repository support persistent identifiers (PID)?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes PID: _____ <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Unknown</p> <p>– <i>If Yes, please indicate the type of PID (e.g., DOI, handle, ARK, PURL, Bibcode, EAN-13, eISSN, IGSN, IISSN, LSID, PMID, UPC, URL, URN).</i></p>
5.6	<p>Under which license will the data be archived and made available for reuse?</p> <p>– <i>Indicate under which license the data may be reused the date in which the license goes into effect.</i></p> <p>❖ <i>Tip: check the Public License Selector (https://ufal.github.io/public-license-selector/) to help you select an appropriate license to deposit your research data for reuse.</i></p>
5.7	<p>Will there be a strategy for publishing specific tools or software generated in this project?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p>– <i>If Yes, please describe your strategy for publishing the analysis software that will be generated in this project. Indicate whether potential users need specific tools or software (e.g., specific scripts, codes or algorithms developed during the project) to access, interpret, and (re-)use the data.</i></p> <p>❖ <i>Recommendation: consider the sustainability of the software needed for accessing and interpreting the data. Check the Five Recommendations for FAIR Software (https://fair-software.nl/).</i></p>
5.8	<p>Will there be other research outputs?</p> <p>– <i>Note: in addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or reused throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g., software, workflows, protocols, models) or physical (e.g., new materials, samples, reagents). Consider which of the questions in this template can apply to the management of other research outputs, and provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for reuse, in line with the FAIR principles.</i></p>

6. RESPONSIBILITIES AND RESOURCES

6.1	<p>Who will be responsible for data management?</p> <p>– <i>Outline the roles and responsibilities for data management/stewardship activities. E.g., data capture, metadata production, data quality, storage and backup, data archiving, and data sharing.</i></p> <p>– <i>For collaborative projects, describe the coordination of data management responsibilities across partners.</i></p> <p>– <i>Indicate who is responsible for implementing the DMP, and for ensuring it is reviewed and, if necessary, revised.</i></p> <p>❖ <i>Recommendation: consider regular updates of the DMP.</i></p>
6.2	<p>What resources will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)?</p> <p>– <i>Indicate and justify any resources (e.g., storage costs, hardware, staff time, costs of preparing data for deposit, repository charges) needed to deliver the data. Describe how the necessary resources to prepare the data for data curation (sharing/preservation) have been costed in. Elaborate on the budget in your grant application, if appropriate.</i></p> <p>– <i>Indicate whether additional resources will be needed to prepare data for deposit or to cover any charges from data repositories. If yes, describe how much is needed and how such costs will be covered.</i></p>

❖ *Tip, Horizon Europe funding: research data/output management costs are eligible for reimbursement during the duration of the project and can be claimed under the conditions defined in the grant agreement.*